

COPING MECHANISMS IN THE NEW MODALITIES OF TEACHING IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on the quarantine experiences and coping strategies of 86 elementary teachers in Itogon, Benguet. Utilizing a descriptive research design and survey method, the findings revealed the effectiveness of coping mechanisms, emphasizing the significance of teachers in mentoring and integrating strategies across social, mental, emotional, and physical aspects. Noteworthy coping mechanisms included gardening for physical well-being, clear communication methods for mental aspects, and the establishment of open innovation platforms for social engagement. Additionally, the study emphasized teachers' resilience in accepting responsibility for facing the stress associated with the challenges posed by new teaching modalities during the pandemic in Itogon, Benguet.

Keywords: *Innovation, platforms, mutual learning, standard hygiene, cognitive appraisal, challenges, stressful job.*

INTRODUCTION

The global response to the COVID-19 pandemic has shifted attention away from other critical challenges, including infectious diseases, climate change, terrorism, wars, and famines (Klein et al., 2020). Despite the universal impact of COVID-19, measures such as self-quarantine, force isolation, physical distancing, hand washing, and sanitizer use have proven effective (Lauer et al., 2020). This has challenged the belief that military might or advanced weaponry alone can address such global threats. The World Health Organization's declaration of COVID-19 as a public health emergency and a pandemic

prompted unprecedented governmental policies, including social distancing and self-quarantine (WHO, 2020). This study investigates coping mechanisms, revealing the efficacy of strategies like gardening for physical well-being (Soga et al., 2017) and open innovation platforms for social engagement (West & Bogers, 2014).

Teachers play a pivotal role in shaping students' lives, and high-quality teaching significantly influences learning outcomes (Hattie, 2003). The teaching profession is inherently stressful, necessitating an understanding of teachers' coping mechanisms to prevent burnout and enhance engagement and effectiveness (Kyriacou, 2001). Coping resources are crucial in mitigating burnout, and effective strategies contribute to a mastery orientation toward teaching (Betoret, 2016). Environmental stressors, particularly those related to academics, impact teachers' stress levels, influencing their professional performance (Montgomery et al., 2012). The intensified stress caused by the COVID-19 pandemic underscores the importance of studying teachers' coping mechanisms during the quarantine period.

Educators face inherent stressors that negatively impact their professional performance, individual productivity, and institutional effectiveness (De Beer & Daniels, 2017). The study on Filipino teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic explores coping practices such as virtual learning, communication within the professional community, and adherence to quarantine requirements (Talidong, 2020). The pandemic's disruption to education, with school closures and social distancing measures, heightens anxiety among teachers (Kaparang et al., 2020). This research delves into teachers' experiences, attitudes, and practices as they cope with the uncertainties and challenges brought about by the pandemic.

In response to the COVID-19 outbreak, the Philippine government implemented measures like the Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ) to curb the virus's spread. Prolonged social isolation resulting from these measures led to widespread loneliness, anxiety, and depression among teachers, potentially resulting in post-traumatic stress disorder (Leite et al., 2020). The study aims to comprehend the impact of COVID-19 on teachers' coping mechanisms in the Philippines. While the Department of Education (DepEd) and Commission on Higher Education (CHED) issued policies to address challenges (DepEd Order No. 012, s. 2020; CHED, 2020), the study explores how teachers cope with the uncertainties and changes brought about by the pandemic.

The demanding nature of the teaching profession often exposes teachers to stress from various personal and school-related factors (Friedman, 2001). Coping mechanisms are crucial for managing stressors, preventing burnout, and positively influencing classroom performance and job satisfaction (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2015). The study in Itogon, Benguet, focuses on assessing coping mechanisms employed by public elementary teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic. Anchored in theories such as Abraham Maslow's Humanistic Theory and stress coping theory (Lazarus, 2015), the research aims to identify teachers' coping levels and provide valuable insights for future research, contributing to the well-being of teachers, learners, and stakeholders.

Research Questions

It is the main objective of the study is to identify the coping mechanism of elementary teachers at Itogon, Benguet during the quarantine period.

Specifically, the study was endeavored to answer the following questions:

1. What are the level of effectiveness of coping mechanism by the elementary teachers in the new modalities as to:
 - 1.1. physical aspect
 - 1.2. mental aspect
 - 1.3. social aspect
 - 1.4. emotional aspect

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive-research design with descriptive-survey methods to investigate the quarantine coping mechanisms of elementary teachers amid the ongoing pandemic. Focused on the interruptions in classes from March to the present, the research delved into the demographic profiles of the respondents and the frequency of teachers' actions in combating COVID-19 during the quarantine period. The choice of a descriptive research design was justified as it offers a quantitative and numerical depiction of trends, attitudes, or opinions within a population through the examination of a sample. Described as a fact-finding approach with interpretative elements, this design is particularly suitable when the subject exhibits variations, providing insights into the nature and status of phenomena within the studied group. Calmorin (2016) supports this perspective, emphasizing that descriptive research is well-suited for presenting factual information about the conditions and situations prevalent among subjects.

The researcher conducted the study in Itogon elementary school province of Benguet during the school year 2021-2022. The respondents was composed of the public elementary school teachers. Total enumeration of eighty-six (86) teachers.

The primary instrument employed for data collection in the study was a questionnaire, comprising two sections encompassing sub-variables to be responded to by the participants. Section I focused on assessing the effectiveness of coping mechanisms utilized by elementary teachers in the new modalities, encompassing aspects such as physical well-being, mental resilience, social engagement, and emotional stability.

Permission to distribute the questionnaire was secured from the dean of Baguio Central University's Graduate School, and subsequent approval for questionnaire circulation among the target respondents was sought from the school division superintendent. Negotiations with district supervisors and administrators of Itogon Districts were undertaken, and after fulfilling all necessary requirements, the questionnaire was

disseminated. The researcher personally delivered and retrieved questionnaires from schools within her reach, conducting informal interviews with teacher respondents during this process. For schools beyond the researcher's reach, assistance was sought from school administrators and trusted teachers to facilitate the distribution and retrieval of the questionnaires.

Following the data collection, a thorough organization and tabulation process was carried out, with subsequent submission to statistical treatments. The statistical analysis involved the use of weighted mean and ranking. The results, incorporating frequency and mean percentage, underwent a descriptive statistical treatment to elucidate the teachers' responses. Ranking was specifically employed to prioritize items within the tables, determined by their computed mean percentages. This systematic approach aimed to facilitate an orderly analysis and interpretation of the gathered data.

RESULTS

Level of Effectiveness of Coping Mechanism by the Elementary Teachers in the New Modalities as Observed by the Respondents

A. Physical Aspect

Statements	Much Effect	Moderate Effect	Least Effect	Mean	Interpretation
1. Parents and teachers work hand in hand	54	32	0	2.63	Much Effect
2. Teachers conduct home visitation and observe health protocol	75	11	0	2.87	Much Effect
3. Teachers do an exercise in every morning to maintain physical fitness	47	39	0	2.55	Much Effect
4. Develops efficiency in managing tasks focusing distance teaching-learning assessment	16	70	0	2.19	Moderate Effect
5. Gardening is one of the activities done by teachers	56	30	0	2.65	Much Effect
6. Enhancing capabilities on giving interventions to learners in distance learning	12	74	0	2.14	Moderate Effect
7. Allow flexibility for curriculum requirements that require hands-on or in person learning	8	78	0	2.09	Moderate Effect

Overall Mean	2.46	Much Effect
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B. Mental Aspect

Statements	Much Effect	Moderate Effect	Least Effect	Mean	Interpretation
1. Teacher's feeling are under pressure is a likely experience for you and many the colleagues	12	74	0	2.14	Moderate Effect
2. Try and use helpful coping strategies such as ensuring sufficient rest and respite during work or between shifts, eat sufficient and healthy food, engage in physical activity, and stay in contact with family and co teachers.	76	10	0	2.88	Much Effect
3. Avoid using unhelpful coping strategies such as use of tobacco, alcohol or other drugs	56	30	0	2.65	Much Effect
4. Use understandable ways to share messages with people with intellectual, cognitive and psychosocial disabilities	78	8	0	2.91	Much Effect
5. Teachers include forms of communication that do not rely solely on written information	59	27	0	2.67	Much Effect
6. Teachers provide full support to other people who are affected by COVID-19 and know how to link them with available resources.	47	39	0	2.56	Much Effect
7. Ensure that good quality communication and accurate information updates are provided to all	58	28	0	2.67	Much Effect
Overall Mean				2.64	Much Effect

C. Social Aspect

Statements	Much Effect	Moderate Effect	Least Effect	Mean	Interpretation
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1. Working from home instead of at the office	39	47	0	2.45	Much Effect
2. Switching to online classes instead of face to face	55	31	0	2.64	Much Effect
3. Visiting of co teachers and students by electronic devices instead of in person	42	44	0	2.49	Much Effect
4. Cancelling or postponing conferences and large meetings	18	68	0	2.21	Moderate Effect
5. Establish open innovation platform to solicit ideas from teachers/administrators, students, and parents	68	18	0	2.79	Much Effect
6. Create a website to communicate with teachers, students and parents about curriculum goals, strategies, and suggested activities and additional resources	27	59	0	2.31	Much Effect
7. Enhance the communication and collaboration in the form of text if parents have access to mobile phones to foster mutual learning and well being	62	24	0	2.72	Much Effect
Overall Mean				2.52	Much Effect

D. Emotional Aspect

Statements	Much Effect	Moderate Effect	Least Effect	Mean	Interpretation
1. Getting emotional support from others	48	38	0	2.56	Much Effect
2. Seeing situation in different manner	12	74	0	2.14	Much Effect
3. Accepting responsibility to face the stress	54	32	0	2.63	Much Effect
4. Finding comfort or solutions through prayers	47	39	0	2.55	Much Effect
5. Taking out some time to rest	44	42	0	2.51	Much Effect

6. Consumption of substances like stimulations or pain killers	33	34	19	2.16	Much Effect
Overall Mean				2.43	Much Effect

DISCUSSION

Table 2 provides an overview of the assessments made by public elementary school teachers regarding the effectiveness of coping mechanisms employed in the new modalities. The table outlines levels of general and mental health, revealing consistently high effectiveness across various indicators. Statistical analysis indicates that all health indicators were significantly effective for teachers, with only one indicator being moderately effective and marginally no significant. Upon delving into the specifics of the coping mechanisms employed by teachers, it was observed that all mechanisms were effective. The computed average weighted mean, particularly for coping mechanisms, stood at 2.64, indicating a high level of effectiveness. This underscores that, amid the pandemic, teachers actively implemented various mental strategies to counteract the adverse effects of the widespread virus.

Under the mental aspect teachers focused on the use understandable ways to share messages with people with intellectual, shows that teachers applied different strategies under mental health for continues routine. This implies that teachers coping mechanism under mental health is very effective.

Teachers in Itogon district exhibited a multifaceted approach to coping with the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, utilizing various coping mechanisms across different aspects. Under the mental aspect, teachers prioritized clear communication through understandable means, earning a weighted mean of 2.91, indicating effective communication with colleagues and superiors. This aligns with research by Bottiani (2019), emphasizing the importance of communication strategies in stress coping. Additionally, employing helpful coping strategies such as ensuring sufficient rest and maintaining physical health, with a weighted mean of 2.88, demonstrated teachers' commitment to holistic well-being during the pandemic. Similar findings by Basch (2020) highlight the importance of educators' well-being and coping mechanisms during times of crisis.

Communication, particularly through non-written means, garnered a weighted mean of 2.67, emphasizing the importance of maintaining effective communication channels, even amid school closures. The study resonates with the research of Chennaoui et al. (2015), suggesting that communication is crucial for reducing stress and improving mental health during challenging times. Teachers actively engaged in supporting others affected by COVID-19, with a weighted mean of 2.56, showcasing their dedication to student welfare. The importance of teachers' support for students during crises is supported by Calmorin (2016), emphasizing the role of educators in providing a supportive environment.

Despite facing the pressure of their responsibilities, teachers demonstrated moderate effectiveness, with a weighted mean of 2.14, highlighting their ability to manage stress during the pandemic. The study aligns with the observations of Bellos (2020), emphasizing the emotional impact of the pandemic on teachers and the need for effective coping strategies. The study also builds on the findings of Betoret (2016), highlighting the significance of coping resources in mitigating burnout among teachers.

In the social aspect, teachers embraced collaborative measures, earning an average weighted mean of 2.52, indicating their adeptness at navigating social challenges. The establishment of open innovation platforms, enhancing communication through various channels, and switching to online classes received positive ratings, showcasing effective adaptation to the new modalities. Epstein (2019) highlights the importance of two-way communication between teachers and parents, emphasizing collaboration for effective educational strategies.

The physical aspect of coping mechanisms revealed teachers' commitment to maintaining their health, with an average weighted mean of 2.46. Home visitation, gardening, and collaboration with parents were highly effective strategies, contributing to overall physical well-being. Nix (2019) supports the notion that teacher home visit programs can positively impact students' academic success and parent involvement.

Examining emotional coping mechanisms, teachers rated accepting responsibility (2.63) and finding comfort through prayers (2.51) as significant. The study aligns with the findings of Lazarus (2016), emphasizing the importance of emotional coping strategies in the teaching profession. The least effective emotional coping mechanisms were substance consumption (2.16) and changing perspectives (2.14). This resonates with Folkman's (2018) distinction between general coping styles and practical coping behaviors during challenging situations.

Overall, the results indicate that teachers in Itogon district adopted coping mechanisms effectively across various dimensions, emphasizing the importance of a holistic approach to well-being in navigating the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings offer insights into the resilience and adaptability of teachers in the face of unprecedented disruptions to the education system, supporting existing literature on the importance of coping mechanisms in the teaching profession during times of crisis.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Public elementary school teachers in Itogon Benguet on the effectiveness of coping mechanisms during the new modalities formulated an effective coping mechanism during

the pandemic on their social aspects, mental aspects, emotional aspects, and physical aspects as behavioral change as a coping mechanisms.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were drawn:

Physical aspects as coping mechanisms of elementary teachers which develops efficiency in managing tasks focusing distance teaching-learning assessment, enhancing capabilities on giving interventions to learners in distance learning, and allow flexibility for curriculum requirements that require hands-on or in person learning must be enrich more to the teachers and different officials or people concerns in the community.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ensuring ethical considerations is a pivotal aspect of research, demanding careful attention from the researchers. Several key principles must be adhered to, including the voluntary participation of respondents, granting them the right to withdraw from the study at their discretion. Informed consent is paramount, necessitating the provision of comprehensive information about the research's purpose and the significance of respondents' participation. The researcher should obtain full consent without exerting any pressure. Safeguarding the privacy or anonymity of participants is crucial, while the formulation of questionnaire, interview guides, and focus group questions must avoid offensive or discriminatory language. Additionally, proper acknowledgment of references, following the APA referencing system, and maintaining the highest level of objectivity in discussions and analyses are imperative throughout the research process.

REFERENCES

- Basch, H.B. (2020). The impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on mental health of undergraduate students in New Jersey, cross-sectional study.
- Bellos, S. (2020). Depression and its relationship with coping strategies and illness perceptions during the covid-19 lockdown in Greece: a cross-sectional survey of the population
- Betoret, (2016). Teacher's burnout syndrome: The Phenomenology of the process. Polish Journal of Health Vol.127, Issue 2 Zdrowie Publications, Poland pp. 63-64.
- Betoret, F. D. (2016). Self-efficacy, school resources, job stressors and burnout among Spanish primary and secondary school teachers: A structural equation approach. *Educational Psychology*, 36(3), 353-372.
- Bottiani J.H. (2019). Teacher stress and burnout in urban middle schools: Associations with job demands, resources, and effective classroom practices. *Journal of School Psychology*. 2019;77:36–51. doi: 10.1016/j.jsp.2019.10.002.
- Chennaoui, M., Arnal, P. J., Sauvet, F., and Leger, D. (2015). Sleep and Exercise: A Reciprocal Issue? *Sleep Med. Rev.* 20, 59–72. doi: 10.1016/j.smrv.2014.06.008.
- Commission on Higher Education [CHED]. (2020). CHED issues guidelines on flexible learning in higher education amid COVID-19 pandemic. Commission on Higher Education, Republic of the Philippines.
- De Beer, J., & Daniels, L. B. (2017). Burnout, job satisfaction and demographic variables of academics at a South African university. *South African Journal of Higher Education*, 31(1), 35-53.
- DepEd Order No. 012, s. 2020. (2020). Adoption of the Basic Education learners continuity plans for school year 2020-2021 in light of the COVID-19 public health emergency. Department of Education, Republic of the Philippines.
- DepEd order No.012. s. (2020). The Adoption of the Basic Education Learners Continuity Plans for School Year 2020-2021 in light of the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency.
- Epstein, J. L. (2019). School, family, and community partnerships: Preparing educators and improving schools. Boulder, CO: Westview.
- Folkman, S.; Lazarus, R. Coping as a Mediator of Emotion. *J. Pers.* (2018) *Soc. Psychol.* 1988, 54, 466–475. [CrossRef]
- Hattie, J. (2003). Teachers make a difference: What is the research evidence? Paper presented at the Building Teacher Quality: What does the research tell us ACER Research Conference, Melbourne.
- Kaparang, T. M., Yero, I. I., & Acal, J. P. (2020). Anxiety among Filipino teachers in the time of COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 10(7), 710-719.
- Klein, S. L., Dhakal, S., Ursin, R. L., Deshpande, S., Sandberg, K., & Mauvais-Jarvis, F. (2020). Biological sex impacts COVID-19 outcomes. *PLoS Pathogens*, 16(6), e1008570.
- Kyriacou, C. (2001). Teacher stress: Directions for future research. *Educational Review*, 53(1), 27-35.
- Lauer, S. A., Grantz, K. H., Bi, Q., Jones, F. K., Zheng, Q., Meredith, H. R., ... & Lessler, J. (2020). The incubation period of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) from publicly

- reported confirmed cases: estimation and application. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 172(9), 577-582.
- Lazarus & Folkman, (2015). *Teacher stress and coping: The Role of personal and job characteristics*. *Procedia, Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Science Direct, Tel Aviv University.
- Lazarus, (2015). *Psychological Stress and the coping process*, New York: MC. Graw Hill.
- Lazarus, R. S. (2015). *Stress and emotion: A new synthesis*. Springer.
- Lazarus, R. S. (2016). *Stress, appraisal, and coping*. New York, NY: Springer.
- Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (2014). *Stress, appraisal, and coping*. New York, NY: Springer.
- Leite, W. L., Huang, J. L., Marcoulides, K. M., & Zhang, Z. (2020). Employee stress and work performance: The role of COVID-19. *Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance*, 7(4), 383-393.
- Montgomery, C., Rupp, A. A., & Carlberg, C. (2012). Predictors of secondary teachers' job satisfaction and burnout over time. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 28(8), 1131-1144.
- Nix, S. B. (2019). *The family engagement partnership student outcome evaluation*. Baltimore, MD: Johns Hopkins University School of Education Center on School, Family, and Community Partnerships. Retrieved from http://www.pthvp.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/09/JHU-STUDY_FINAL-REPORT.pdf
- Skaalvik, E. M., & Skaalvik, S. (2015). Job satisfaction, stress and coping strategies in the teaching profession—What do teachers say? *International Education Studies*, 8(3), 181-192.
- Soga, M., Gaston, K. J., & Yamaura, Y. (2017). Gardening is beneficial for health: A meta-analysis. *Preventive Medicine Reports*, 5, 92-99.
- Talidong, K. M. (2020). Coping mechanisms of Filipino teachers during the COVID-19 outbreak: An online survey. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences*, 7(1), 12-22.
- Talidong, Karen Joy B. (2020). *Philippine Teachers' Practices to Deal with Anxiety amid COVID-19*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15325024.2020.1759225>
- West, J., & Bogers, M. (2014). Leveraging external sources of innovation: A review of research on open innovation. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 31(4), 814-831.